

Development and scalability of a 2Tb/s Data transmission Module based on a 3um SOI Silicon Photonics platform.

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ABSTRACT:

VTT's well-proven 3 μm SOI (Silicon Over Insulator) photonic integration platform is particularly suitable for passive optical functionalities such as Multiplexers, De-Multiplexers, Power Splitters, Delay Lines, Mach-Zehnder Interferometers (MZI), also for active operations such as phase tuning through Thermo-optic Switches and optical power monitoring or high-speed detection with integrated Ge Photo-Detectors (Ge-PD) etc. In combination with integrated up-reflecting mirrors and solder coated cavities it's enabling heterogeneous integration of III-V active devices; both Wafer Level Packaging (WLP) and E/O Wafer Level Tests can be fully exploited, scaling up in volume manufacturing while dramatically reducing assembly costs.

Here heterogeneous integration of 40 Vertical Cavity Surface Emitting Lasers (VCSELs) and a SOI 40:1 multiplexer Photonic Integrated Circuit (PIC) is exploited with flip-chip techniques, coupling VCSEL emitting spots on top of respective up-reflective mirrors. VCSELs can be directly modulated up to 50Gb/s reaching a 2Tb/s full transmission capacity. Additional 40 linear VCSEL drivers are flip-chip bonded onto a suitable Land Grid Array (LGA) interposer designed to provide interconnection and thermal decoupling capabilities to the Si-PIC, realizing a very compact, thermally efficient packaging solution. The exit waveguide from the PIC is also terminated with an up-reflective mirror and furthermore coupled with a 90 deg. tilting fiber optic pigtail designed to minimize the form-factor impact, improving mechanical reliability of the overall transmitter module.

1. SYSTEM CONSIDERATIONS

In EU_PASSION project, a transmitter module (MOD1) has been conceived to exploit Sliceable Bandwidth and bit rate Variable Transceiver (S-BVT) in agile metro networks^{[1] [2]} to adaptively and efficiently use the operating spectrum in multiple dimensions, such as polarization multiplexing. Therefore, data transmission capacity of tens of Tb/s per spatial channel, more than 100 Tb/s per link and Pb/s per node can be achievable. A Silicon Photonics Integrated Circuit (PIC) and VCSEL light sources have been efficiently combined together^{[3][5]} to maximize the data transmission energy efficiency within 5 pJ/bit including driving electronics. In MOD1, heterogeneous integration of forty InP 1,55um VCSEL sources (provided by VERTILAS GmbH) properly tuned to result 25-GHz spaced in wavelength each other, are DMT directly modulated up to 50 Gb/s to target up to 8-Tb/s WDM aggregated capacity for a single polarization state. Furthermore, a 16 Tb/s transmission capacity per spatial channel is achievable exploiting polarization-division multiplexing. A spatial dimension provided by a 7 cores MCF or more simply a bundle of 7 fibers could enable up to 112 Tb/s aggregated capacity per link as depicted in Fig. 1.

Figure 1 Modular approach and polarization multiplexing to exploit aggregated capacity up to 112TB/s per link

MOD1 functional block is essentially constitute by 4 sub-modules each one contains 10 VCSELs. The total 40 wavelength emissions cover the entire C-band with 100 GHz granularity as shown in Fig.2. VCSELs' operating wavelengths are spaced on the entire C-band with 25GHz granularity. To maximize the use of available VCSELs, fine wavelength tuning can be obtained with thermal and current adjustments, although for practical and remote control reasons only current tuning has been adopted for this development. Applying a 50-Gb/s driving modulation to each VCSEL, an aggregated capacity of 2 Tb/s per module is achievable.

Figure 2 MOD1 basic concept

SILICON PHOTONICS CHIP DESIGN

MOD1 PIC design is based on a robust 3 μ m-thick SOI photonic integration platform and consists in the integration of four identical “S” shaped 10:1 Arrayed Waveguide Gratings multiplexers (MUX 1-4) Their output waveguides are furthermore routed into a 4:1 multiplexer stage (MUX 5) realized with a cascade of three Mach-Zehnder interferometers having Thermo-Optic (TO) elements^[4]. Phase control of those TO micro-heaters results in precise optical level balancing among MZI arms and the output power at the exit port. All input waveguides are terminated with 45deg. up-reflective mirrors allowing VCSELs to be flip-chip bonded on top while coupling their optical beams into SOI waveguides. Similarly, the output waveguide (exit port) of the PIC is also terminated with an up-reflective mirror, enabling a vertical tilt of the exit-beam toward a micro-optic, GRIN-based, fiber pigtailed periscope. This special arrangement has been specifically designed to result flat and parallel to the SOI surface of the PIC, overcoming vertical and bulky fiber-block assemblies (such as those used for coupling gratings) dramatically improving the intrinsic reliability and overall form-factor of the module. The main PIC layout and the periscope coupling concept is shown in Fig.3.

Figure 3 PIC main layout and periscope-coupling concept

1.1. ARRAYED WAVEGUIDE GRATING (AWG) DESIGN

In MOD1 PIC, a “S” shaped 10:1 AWG design has been selected among other multiplexing solutions due to its good tolerance during manufacturing processes, a well-established behavioral modeling and finally a comprehensive VTT Photonic Design Kit (PDK) availability. On-chip insertion loss of about 1.6 ± 0.4 dB, and a cross talk lower than -20 dB has been achieved, as shown in Fig. 4.

Figure 4 1x10, 400GHz ch/spacing AWG with low loss and low cross-talk

2.2 VCSEL and UP-REFLECTIVE MIRROR INTEGRATION

Up-reflective mirrors design, working with Total Internal Reflection (TIR) are also standard-available in the VTT PDK and selected for their highest reflection coefficient. This approach is instrumental to efficiently couple VCSELs output beams into input waveguides, which principle and assembly steps are shown in Fig.5

Figure 5 Schematic view and FIB cross-section of a 45° up-reflecting mirror coupled with a 3um SOI waveguide and coupling losses measured after VCSEL flip-chip bonding.

Up-reflective mirror coupling-losses when interfacing a SM (PM) fiber has been measured lower than 0.5 dB in both TM/TE polarizations over the entire C-band [6]. Total coupling losses of a VCSEL on top of an up-reflective mirror is reported to be 4.4dB and 4.1dB respectively.

2. LGA INTERPOSER and MODULE INTEGRATION

MOD1 design requires accurate electrical, thermal and opto-mechanical interconnection solutions overall performed by a single electrical interposer based on an 8 layers 600um thick, ENEPIG-finished, Panasonic Megtron7 substrate. A Land Grid Array (LGA) architecture has been selected to perform external electrical interconnections and a Re-Distribution Layers design (RDL) routing 40 x100Ω GSSG differential lines for VCSEL-drivers inputs as well as 648 DC lines (including ground distribution, DC voltage and digital controls) for a total amount of 808 pads, has been designed and realized. A fully packaged overview of MOD1 with LGA interposer, completed with sealed upper and lower lids, is show in Fig.6

Figure 6 MOD1 fully packaged with LGA interposer and sealed with upper and lower lids

Constant temperature operations are required for PIC and VCSELs to prevent uncontrolled thermally-induced wavelength shifts due to SOI intrinsic $\Delta\lambda/\Delta t$ thermal drift of approx 70pm/K. In one hand, an active cooling solution with an externally-mounted, high-COP thermoelectric cooler (TEC) is adopted. To minimize its power consumption both PIC and VCSELs has been designed to operate at $+40^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 0.1^{\circ}\text{C}$ which is a good trade-off to obtain a reasonable optical output power with the lowest TEC dissipated power in the $-5^{\circ}\text{C} \div +70^{\circ}\text{C}$ operating range. On the other hand, 40 linear drivers with more than 25-GHz analog bandwidth needed to directly modulate corresponding VCSELs are not required to operate at constant temperature. Therefore their total dissipated heats (approx 12W) are not handled by TEC but simply dissipated in still air (at max $+50^{\circ}\text{C}$ ambient temperature), through a passive heatsink. To reduce parasitic heat flows moving from the interposer hottest areas (where drivers are mounted) to the silicon PIC, a precise 200um thermal insulating air-gap separating the PIC four side edges and the interposer, has been observed, as shown in Fig.7.

Figure 7 MOD1 interposer with (flip-chip bonded) VCSEL-drivers is air-gap thermally decoupled to corresponding (flip-chip bonded) VCSELS on PIC

4 CONCLUSION

In this paper an integrated transmitter module showing up to 2-Tb/s data capacity based on VTT 3um Silicon Over Insulator (SOI) Photonics Integrated Chip (PIC) is described. This module represents a key building block in the exploitation of multi-Tb/s S-BVTs operating with 25-GHz granularity, like those conceived in EU_PASSION project. Such remarkable transmission capacity is provided by a PIC with wavelength multiplexing functionalities in combination of a cluster of 40 InP VCSELS, designed to be directly modulated up to 50 Gb/s and optically coupled on top of up-reflective TIR mirrors with flip-chip soldering techniques. Accurate active and passive thermal paths provide PIC constant temperature operations and large cooling temperature excursion of VCSEL-drivers with negligible mutual influences. Finally, an innovative LGA electrical interposer with more than 800 pads assures whole RF and control lines routing and external electrical interconnection.

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